

Complete Solution of the Einstein Field Equations for a Spherical Shell of Truly Incompressible Liquid

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Abstract

We present the solution of the Einstein field equations, in the static and spherically symmetric case, for an incompressible fluid, that has constant *proper* energy density at each and every point of the volume where it exists, according to a set of local observers who are stationary with respect to the fluid at each point. In the general case the fluid exists within a spherically symmetric shell with an inner vacuum-matter interface at a radial position r_1 and an outer matter-vacuum interface at a radial position r_2 in the Schwarzschild coordinate system. Therefore, in the general case there is an inner vacuum region with a repulsive singularity at the origin, just like in all other similar shell solutions. We present the parameter plane of the problem, and show that there are limits of solutions that approach the configuration of black holes, with the formation of an event horizon at the radial position r_2 .

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1 Introduction

Shortly after Einstein completed and published the theory of General Relativity [1] in 1915, Karl Schwarzschild found and published the well-known solution for the spherically symmetric and static problem of General Relativity in vacuum [2], that is now known as the “Exterior Schwarzschild Solution”. Less well known, and perhaps of more limited usefulness and impact, he also found and published a solution of that theory within a spherically symmetric matter distribution [3], valid within a sphere of fluid with an energy density which is constant with the Schwarzschild radial coordinate r , a solution which is now known as the “Interior Schwarzschild Solution”. These two solutions can be tied together by means of appropriate interface boundary conditions at the single matter-vacuum interface between them, in order to form the complete solution for the gravitational problem of a sphere of liquid fluid with an energy density having the stated property.

More recently, we were able to generalize this interior Schwarzschild solution, which is valid for matter-filled spheres, to solutions for spherically symmetric shells of liquid fluid located between two radial positions r_1 and r_2 , in the Schwarzschild coordinate system [4]. While the interior Schwarzschild solution is in fact a two-parameter family of solutions, that can be parametrized for example by its total mass M and by the radial position r_0 of the sphere of fluid, this new set of solutions forms a three-parameter family, that can be parametrized by M , r_1 and r_2 . These new extended solutions converge back to the interior Schwarzschild solutions when we make $r_1 \rightarrow 0$ and $r_2 = r_0$. This new family of solutions introduces new concepts regarding the character of singularities in General Relativity. All of this was discussed at length in [4].

The type of liquid fluid that exists in these interior solutions, for either filled spheres or shells, is frequently described in the literature as an “incompressible fluid”. This is, however, not quite true, and constitutes in fact something of an abuse of language. While it is true that in all such solutions the energy density $\rho(r)$ is a constant ρ_0 when expressed in terms of Schwarzschild coordinates, it does *not* really correspond to an uniform *proper* distribution of energy, because in these solutions the three-dimensional space, under the effects of gravity, curves underneath the energy distribution, so that the amount of energy per unit of proper volume is *not* constant along the fluid. If a fluid is truly incompressible, then a set of local observers, one at each given point of the fluid, each one at rest with respect to the fluid at that point, who measure at each point the proper energy contained within a small proper volume around that point, should come up with the same value of the proper energy density, at all points where the fluid exists.

The rather arbitrary mathematical choice of making the energy density $\rho(r)$ constant with r is just an algebraic simplification that allows one to write down exact solutions of the Einstein field equations in closed form, as was done in [3] and [4]. It does not correspond to any sensible or particularly simple physical condition on the matter itself. This choice just simplifies the mathematics, nothing more. It is therefore to be expected that the problem with a constant proper energy density will be somewhat harder to solve, as we will indeed verify here. In this paper we will solve the problem of finding the spacetime geometry, the energy density and the pressure for a static and spherically symmetric distribution of truly incompressible fluid, with a constant proper energy density. After the differential equations are derived, and some of the basic properties of the solutions are obtained by analytical means, and in contrast with the character of the results in [3] and [4], the solution will ultimately have to be determined in detail by numerical means.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we state the problem and work out the analytical part of the resolution; in Section 3 we work out the elements for the numerical

part of the resolution; in Section 4 we present and discuss the numerical results; and in Section 5 we present our conclusions.

2 Statement of the Problem

We will present here, in the case of a spherically symmetric shell of incompressible liquid with constant proper energy density, the solution of the Einstein field equations of General Relativity [5],

$$R_{\mu}^{\nu} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\mu}^{\nu} = -\kappa T_{\mu}^{\nu}, \quad (1)$$

where $\kappa = 8\pi G/c^4$, G is the universal gravitational constant and c is the speed of light. Under the conditions of time independence and of spherical symmetry around the spatial origin of the Schwarzschild system of coordinates (t, r, θ, ϕ) , the most general possible metric is given by the invariant interval, written in terms of this spherical system of coordinates,

$$ds^2 = e^{2\nu(r)} c^2 dt^2 - e^{2\lambda(r)} dr^2 - r^2 [d\theta^2 + \sin^2(\theta) d\phi^2], \quad (2)$$

where $\exp[2\nu(r)]$ and $\exp[2\lambda(r)]$ are two positive functions of only r . As one can see above, in this paper we will use the time-like signature $(+, -, -, -)$, following [5]. Under these conditions the mixed-index matter stress-energy tensor density T_{μ}^{ν} on the right-hand side of the equation is diagonal, and given by the four diagonal components $T_0^0(r) = \rho(r)$, where $\rho(r)$ is the energy density of the matter, and $T_1^1(r) = T_2^2(r) = T_3^3(r) = -P(r)$, where $P(r)$ is its pressure, which is isotropic, as is required for a fluid.

Our first task here is to determine the form of $\rho(r)$ that corresponds to a constant proper energy density. Given an element of coordinate spatial volume $dr \times r d\theta \times r \sin(\theta) d\phi$, if we use $\rho(r) = \rho_0$ then ρ_0 is the constant quantity of energy δE_C per unit of *coordinate* spatial volume,

$$\delta E_C = \rho_0 r^2 \sin(\theta) dr d\theta d\phi. \quad (3)$$

However, as one can see in Equation (2), the element of proper spatial volume contained within this element of coordinate spatial volume is given by a different expression, which can be written as $\exp[\lambda(r)] dr \times r d\theta \times r \sin(\theta) d\phi$, so that in this case ρ_0 is a constant amount of energy δE_P per unit of *proper* spatial volume, expressed as

$$\delta E_P = \rho_0 r^2 e^{\lambda(r)} \sin(\theta) dr d\theta d\phi. \quad (4)$$

If we want to express this physical situation, namely that of a homogeneous distribution of proper density of energy, in terms of an energy density $\rho(r)$ in Schwarzschild coordinates, then we must impose that

$$\rho(r) r^2 \sin(\theta) dr d\theta d\phi = \rho_0 r^2 e^{\lambda(r)} \sin(\theta) dr d\theta d\phi, \quad (5)$$

from which it follows at once that, in order to have a constant proper energy density ρ_0 , within a shell from the inner radial position r_1 to the outer radial position r_2 , we must use the coordinate energy density given in Schwarzschild coordinates by

$$\rho(r) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } 0 \leq r < r_1, \\ \rho_0 e^{\lambda(r)} & \text{for } r_1 < r < r_2, \\ 0 & \text{for } r_2 < r < \infty, \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where r_1 is the radial position of the inner vacuum-matter interface and r_2 is the radial position of the outer matter-vacuum interface. This determines, therefore, the form of $\rho(r)$ for our problem here, in terms of the radial metric coefficient function $\lambda(r)$. Note that $\rho(r)$ is discontinuous at the matter-vacuum interfaces. However, $P(r)$ must still be continuous, and hence we must have that $P(r_1) = 0$ and that $P(r_2) = 0$ at the matter-vacuum interfaces, which constitute part of the interface boundary conditions of the problem.

The next step is to derive the explicit form of the differential equations for this case. In [4] we showed that the field equations in Equation (1) can be reduced, in the static and spherically symmetric case, in Schwarzschild coordinates, to the set of three first-order differential equations

$$[1 - 2r\lambda'(r)] e^{-2\lambda(r)} = 1 - \kappa r^2 \rho(r), \quad (7)$$

$$[1 + 2r\nu'(r)] e^{-2\lambda(r)} = 1 + \kappa r^2 P(r), \quad (8)$$

$$[P(r) + \rho(r)] \nu'(r) = -P'(r), \quad (9)$$

where the primes indicate differentiation with respect to r and where Equation (9) above is a consistency condition derived from the Bianchi identity of the Ricci curvature tensor. Note that the left-hand side of Equation (7) above can be written as a total derivative. If we now transform to a dimensionless radial variable ξ and associated parameters, as well as to dimensionless versions of the functions $\rho(r)$ and $P(r)$, given by

$$\xi = r/r_0, \quad (10)$$

$$\xi_1 = r_1/r_0, \quad (11)$$

$$\xi_2 = r_2/r_0, \quad (12)$$

$$\bar{\rho}_0 = \kappa r_0^2 \rho_0, \quad (13)$$

$$\bar{\rho}(\xi) = \kappa r_0^2 \rho(\xi), \quad (14)$$

$$\bar{P}(\xi) = \kappa r_0^2 P(\xi), \quad (15)$$

where r_0 is an arbitrary reference value, a fixed radial position, that for the time being remains unspecified, then we can write these equations as

$$[\xi e^{-2\lambda(\xi)}]' = 1 - \xi^2 \bar{\rho}(\xi), \quad (16)$$

$$[1 + 2\xi\nu'(\xi)] e^{-2\lambda(\xi)} = 1 + \xi^2 \bar{P}(\xi), \quad (17)$$

$$\nu'(\xi) = -\frac{\bar{P}'(\xi)}{\bar{P}(\xi) + \bar{\rho}(\xi)}, \quad (18)$$

where the primes now indicate differentiation with respect to ξ . We now make one more transformation of variables, from the metric function $\lambda(\xi)$ to the function $\gamma(\xi)$ defined by the relation

$$e^{2\lambda(\xi)} = \frac{\xi}{\xi - \gamma(\xi)}, \quad (19)$$

thus leading to the simplification of Equation (16)

$$\begin{aligned} [\xi - \gamma(\xi)]' &= 1 - \xi^2 \bar{\rho}(\xi) \Rightarrow \\ \gamma'(\xi) &= \xi^2 \bar{\rho}(\xi), \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

and to the simplification of Equation (17),

$$\begin{aligned} [1 + 2\xi\nu'(\xi)] \left[1 - \frac{\gamma(\xi)}{\xi}\right] &= 1 + \xi^2 \bar{P}(\xi) \Rightarrow \\ 2\nu'(\xi) [\xi - \gamma(\xi)] &= \frac{\gamma(\xi)}{\xi} + \xi^2 \bar{P}(\xi) \Rightarrow \\ \nu'(\xi) &= \frac{\gamma(\xi) + \xi^3 \bar{P}(\xi)}{2\xi [\xi - \gamma(\xi)]}. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Using now the expression in Equation (6) for the energy density within the matter region, and the expression in Equation (19) for $\lambda(\xi)$, we therefore have for our set of three equations

$$\gamma'(\xi) = \xi^2 \bar{\rho}_0 \sqrt{\frac{\xi}{\xi - \gamma(\xi)}}, \quad (22)$$

$$\nu'(\xi) = \frac{\gamma(\xi) + \xi^3 \bar{P}(\xi)}{2\xi [\xi - \gamma(\xi)]}, \quad (23)$$

$$\nu'(\xi) = -\frac{\bar{P}'(\xi)}{\bar{P}(\xi) + \bar{\rho}_0 \sqrt{\xi/[\xi - \gamma(\xi)]}}. \quad (24)$$

Note that, since $\bar{\rho}_0$ is necessarily non-negative, Equation (22) implies that $\gamma'(\xi) \geq 0$, which in turn implies that $\gamma(\xi)$ is a monotonically increasing function, that is constant if and only if $\bar{\rho}_0 = 0$, that is, within vacuum regions. Note also that this first equation, giving $\gamma'(\xi)$, involves only the function $\gamma(\xi)$ itself and has therefore decoupled from the other two functions and corresponding equations. This equation can be solved by itself, independently of the functions $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$. We can obtain an equation giving $\bar{P}'(\xi)$ by eliminating $\nu'(\xi)$ in Equations (23) and (24), thus leading to

$$\bar{P}'(\xi) = -\frac{1}{2\xi} \frac{\gamma(\xi) + \xi^3 \bar{P}(\xi)}{\xi - \gamma(\xi)} \left[\bar{P}(\xi) + \bar{\rho}_0 \sqrt{\frac{\xi}{\xi - \gamma(\xi)}} \right]. \quad (25)$$

This equation giving $\bar{P}'(\xi)$ has decoupled from the function $\nu(\xi)$ and the corresponding equation. It can be solved together with the equation giving $\gamma'(\xi)$, independently of the function $\nu(\xi)$. We have therefore the final form of our set of three differential equations, in coupling order,

$$\gamma'(\xi) = \xi^2 \bar{\rho}_0 \sqrt{\frac{\xi}{\xi - \gamma(\xi)}}, \quad (26)$$

$$\bar{P}'(\xi) = -\frac{\gamma(\xi) + \xi^3 \bar{P}(\xi)}{2\xi [\xi - \gamma(\xi)]} \left[\bar{P}(\xi) + \bar{\rho}_0 \sqrt{\frac{\xi}{\xi - \gamma(\xi)}} \right], \quad (27)$$

$$\nu'(\xi) = \frac{\gamma(\xi) + \xi^3 \bar{P}(\xi)}{2\xi [\xi - \gamma(\xi)]}. \quad (28)$$

The solutions of these equations in the inner and outer vacuum regions are well known. The solution in the inner vacuum region was derived in [4], and is given by

$$0 < \xi < \xi_1 : \begin{cases} e^{2\lambda(\xi)} = \frac{\xi}{\xi + \xi_\mu}, \\ e^{2\nu(\xi)} = \frac{1 - \xi_M/\xi_2}{1 + \xi_\mu/\xi_1} \frac{\xi + \xi_\mu}{\xi}, \\ \bar{\rho}(\xi) = 0, \\ \bar{P}(\xi) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

while in the outer vacuum region it is the exterior Schwarzschild solution, given by

$$\xi_2 < \xi < \infty : \begin{cases} e^{2\lambda(\xi)} = \frac{\xi}{\xi - \xi_M}, \\ e^{2\nu(\xi)} = \frac{\xi - \xi_M}{\xi}, \\ \bar{\rho}(\xi) = 0, \\ \bar{P}(\xi) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

In these solutions the dimensionless parameters indicated are defined by

$$\xi_\mu = r_\mu/r_0, \quad (31)$$

$$\xi_M = r_M/r_0, \quad (32)$$

where r_M is the Schwarzschild radius and r_μ is a new parameter with dimensions of length that is introduced into the problem by the interface boundary conditions.

We can now see that the function $\gamma(\xi)$ defined in Equation (19) operates as a kind of mass function for the distribution of matter. From Equation (20) we have for the dimensionless energy density that $\bar{\rho}(\xi) = \gamma'(\xi)/\xi^2$, so that if we integrate this dimensionless matter energy density over the volume V_S of a spherically symmetric shell between ξ_a and ξ_b we get

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{V_S} d^3\chi \bar{\rho}(\xi) &= 4\pi \int_{\xi_a}^{\xi_b} d\xi \xi^2 \bar{\rho}(\xi) \\ &= 4\pi \int_{\xi_a}^{\xi_b} d\xi \gamma'(\xi) \\ &= 4\pi [\gamma(\xi_b) - \gamma(\xi_a)], \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

where $\chi^\mu = x^\mu/r_0$ are dimensionless coordinates. If we now choose ξ_a to be the single zero $\xi_z = r_z/r_0$ of the function $\gamma(\xi)$, and also choose $\xi_b = \xi_2$, then we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{V_S} d^3\chi \bar{\rho}(\xi) &= 4\pi\gamma(\xi_2) \\ &= 4\pi\xi_M, \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

where we used the fact that, from Equations (19) and (30), we have that $\gamma(\xi_2) = \xi_M$. For values of ξ to the right of ξ_2 the function $\gamma(\xi)$ stays constant at the value ξ_M . In terms of dimensionfull parameters and functions the relation above reduces to

$$\int_{V_S} d^3x \rho(r) = Mc^2, \quad (35)$$

which is the rest energy associated to the total mass M of the shell. Note however that the function $\gamma(\xi)$ for the shell solutions does not have the same meaning usually assumed for the mass function in solutions within filled spheres. Note that the integral discussed above is *not* taken over the whole volume of the shell of matter, that goes from ξ_1 to ξ_2 . While $\gamma(\xi)$ interpolates masses from 0 to the total mass M for ξ in the interval $[\xi_z, \xi_2]$, it has negative values to the left of its root ξ_z , and is constant at the negative value $-\xi_\mu$ within the inner vacuum region. When a shell solution is made to converge to a filled sphere solution, by making $\xi_1 \rightarrow 0$, then the zero ξ_z of $\gamma(\xi)$ converges to $\xi = 0$, and the mass function recovers its more usual behavior and meaning.

Note that from Equation (26) it follows that, once we hit a matter-vacuum interface coming from within the matter region, where $\bar{\rho}_0$ suddenly becomes zero, as can be seen in Equation (6), from that point on we have that $\gamma'(\xi) \equiv 0$, and hence that $\gamma(\xi)$ becomes a constant, as expected. Note also that from Equation (27) it follows that, once we hit a matter-vacuum interface coming from within the matter region, and hence $\bar{P}(\xi)$ has hit the value zero, and since at that point $\bar{\rho}_0$ also suddenly becomes zero, from that point on we have both that $\bar{P}'(\xi) \equiv 0$ and that $\bar{P}(\xi) \equiv 0$, thus confirming the solution for $\bar{P}(\xi)$ within the two vacuum regions. We therefore see that indeed we already have the complete solution of the problem in the two vacuum regions. Finally, note that from Equations (27) and (28) we have that at a certain extremum point $\xi_e = r_e/r_0$ within the matter region it holds that both $\bar{P}'(\xi_e) = 0$ and $\nu'(\xi_e) = 0$, that point being defined by the relation

$$\bar{P}(\xi_e) = -\frac{\gamma(\xi_e)}{\xi_e^3}, \quad (36)$$

which, given that $\bar{P}(\xi)$ is necessarily positive, implies that at this point we have $\gamma(\xi_e) < 0$, so that ξ_e must be located to the left of the single zero ξ_z of the function $\gamma(\xi)$. The point ξ_e corresponds, therefore, to extrema of both $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$. In the case of $\bar{P}(\xi)$ it is the single point of maximum, and in the case of $\nu(\xi)$ it is the single point of minimum.

3 Numerical Resolution

The Equations (26) through (28) lead to a fairly simple set of numerical development equations. Using the two temporary functions given by

$$F_1(\xi, \gamma) = \sqrt{\frac{\xi}{\xi - \gamma(\xi)}}, \quad (37)$$

$$F_2(\xi, \gamma, \bar{P}) = \frac{\gamma(\xi) + \xi^3 \bar{P}(\xi)}{2\xi[\xi - \gamma(\xi)]}, \quad (38)$$

where $F_1(\xi, \gamma)$ is just another name for the radial metric coefficient $\exp[\lambda(\xi)]$, they result in the set of three numerical development equations for the functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$,

$$\delta\gamma(\xi) = \left\{ \xi^2 \bar{\rho}_0 F_1(\xi, \gamma) \right\} \delta\xi, \quad (39)$$

$$\delta\bar{P}(\xi) = \left\{ -F_2(\xi, \gamma, \bar{P}) [\bar{P}(\xi) + \bar{\rho}_0 F_1(\xi, \gamma)] \right\} \delta\xi, \quad (40)$$

$$\delta\nu(\xi) = \left\{ F_2(\xi, \gamma, \bar{P}) \right\} \delta\xi. \quad (41)$$

This numerical system can be used to determine the three unknown functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$ within the matter region. However, in order to do that we must first consider the

initial conditions for the integration. Here there are two ways in which we can proceed. For example, we can start the integration at the radial position ξ_2 of the external interface and integrate backward, towards the radial position ξ_1 of the internal interface. The initial conditions at ξ_2 , using some initial value $\xi_M < \xi_2$ for the parameter ξ_M , can be written as

$$\gamma(\xi_2) = \xi_M, \quad (42)$$

$$\bar{P}(\xi_2) = 0, \quad (43)$$

$$\nu(\xi_2) = -\frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{\xi_2}{\xi_2 - \xi_M}\right), \quad (44)$$

where the values for $\gamma(\xi_2)$ and $\nu(\xi_2)$ are obtained from Equation (19) and the exterior Schwarzschild solution shown in Equation (30), which is valid for $\xi \geq \xi_2$, as well as from the fact that the functions $\gamma(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$ must be continuous. The numerical stop criterion leading to the determination of the radial position $\xi_1 < \xi_2$ is simply that one finds a second zero of $\bar{P}(\xi)$, that is, that one eventually gets $\bar{P}(\xi_1) = 0$, which determines the point ξ_1 . At that point we also find the value of ξ_μ , by means of the relation $\gamma(\xi_1) = -\xi_\mu$, according to the relation in Equation (19) and the solution within the inner vacuum region seen in Equation (29), given that $\gamma(\xi)$ must be continuous. In this way we determine the four basic numbers, ξ_1 , ξ_2 , ξ_M and ξ_μ , that completely characterize a given solution. Once we get to the position ξ_1 the numerical integration can be halted, since below ξ_1 we have the internal vacuum solution, which we have in closed form, as can be seen in Equation (29).

There will be an implicit consistency condition involving the values of ξ_2 , ξ_M , and $\bar{\rho}_0$. Given initial values ξ_2 and ξ_M , for each value used for the parameter $\bar{\rho}_0$ a value of ξ_1 is to be determined. Given a set of initial values, if a second zero of $\bar{P}(\xi)$ cannot be found for some non-negative value of ξ , then there is no solution for that set of initial values. We must always start with some $\xi_M < \xi_2$, in order to avoid an external event horizon, but depending on the relative values of ξ_M and $\bar{\rho}_0$, the search downward for a second zero of $\bar{P}(\xi)$ may fail, resulting in the absence of an inner vacuum region and in a hard singularity of the matter energy density at the spatial origin.

Alternatively, one may also start at the radial position ξ_1 and integrate forward, up to the radial position ξ_2 . In this case the value of ξ_M will not be determined a priori. Instead, one will have to choose a value of ξ_μ to start with. In this case the stop criterion is that we find a second point $\xi_2 > \xi_1$ where we have that $\bar{P}(\xi_2) = 0$. At that point we also determine ξ_M , from the relation $\gamma(\xi_2) = \xi_M$, according to the relation in Equation (19) and the exterior Schwarzschild solution seen in Equation (30). In this way we once again determine the four basic numbers, ξ_1 , ξ_2 , ξ_M and ξ_μ , that completely characterize a given solution. Just as before, once we get to the position ξ_2 the numerical integration can be halted, since above ξ_2 we have the exterior Schwarzschild solution, which we also have in closed form, as can be seen in Equation (30).

Again there is an implicit consistency condition, this time involving the values of ξ_1 , ξ_μ and $\bar{\rho}_0$. In this case, given initial values ξ_1 and ξ_μ , for each value used for the parameter $\bar{\rho}_0$ a value of ξ_2 is to be determined. Given a set of initial values, there could be a failure to find an acceptable value for ξ_2 because the condition $\xi_M < \xi_2$ may fail to be satisfied during the whole extent of the forward integration process. In other words, as one integrates forward one may find that the total mass $M(\xi)$ within the sphere at the radial position ξ increases too fast, so that the corresponding value of $\gamma(\xi)$ crosses above the current value of ξ at some point, before a value for ξ_2 is found, thus leading to the singular condition $\xi_M > \xi_2$. Once again, in this case there is no solution for the chosen set of initial conditions. In this forward integration case the initial conditions would be given by

$$\gamma(\xi_1) = -\xi_\mu, \quad (45)$$

$$\bar{P}(\xi_1) = 0, \quad (46)$$

$$\nu(\xi_1) = \nu_0 - \frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{\xi_1}{\xi_1 + \xi_\mu}\right), \quad (47)$$

where the values of $\gamma(\xi_1)$ and $\nu(\xi_1)$ are obtained from Equation (19) and the inner vacuum solution shown in Equation (29), which is valid for $\xi \leq \xi_1$, as well as from the fact that the functions $\gamma(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$ must be continuous. However, in this case, since the values of ξ_2 and ξ_M are still unknown at this point, the value of the constant ν_0 has to be adjusted a posteriori, so that when we get to ξ_2 the function $\nu(\xi)$ has at that point the correct value given by the exterior Schwarzschild solution. We can start the run at ξ_1 with $\nu_0 = 0$ and readjust the value of the whole function $\nu(\xi)$ once we get to ξ_2 , using then the value of $\nu(\xi)$ at the external interface, as given in Equation (44).

In all the runs that produced the data for the graphs displayed in this paper we used the backward integration alternative, starting with values of ξ_2 , ξ_M and $\bar{\rho}_0$. In this way we used the parameters ξ_2 and $\bar{\rho}_0$ to map the parameter plane of the solutions. For ξ_M we simply used $\xi_M = 1$, which means only that $r_M = r_0$, and therefore represents no more than a choice of value for the arbitrary parameter r_0 . Since in this case we have that $\xi_2 \rightarrow 1$ corresponds to the formation of an event horizon at the radial position ξ_2 , so that we must have $\xi_2 > 1$, the parameter plane was plotted for the variables $(\xi_2 - 1)$ and $\bar{\rho}_0$, both starting from zero, as can be seen in Figure 10.

As we will see, given a value for $\xi_2 > 1$ there is a minimum possible value of $\bar{\rho}_0$, below which we have that either the Dominant Energy Condition (or DEC for short) is violated or the backward integration process produces a hard singularity of $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ at the spatial origin. On the other hand, there seems to be no upper limit for the values of $\bar{\rho}_0$. Therefore, in this problem the curves that we usually name the DEC curve and the Tooper curve coincide as the same limiting curve. Although this problem is quite outside the scope of the solutions originally found by Tooper [6] for polytropes, we will still refer to the solutions over this limiting curve as the Tooper solutions. Along one part of the limiting curve, for sufficiently large ξ_2 , above the transition point located approximately at $\xi_2 \simeq 1.33$, they do satisfy the essential conditions used by Tooper, leading to the absence of the inner vacuum region and of the central singularity that it contains. Therefore, in this region of the limiting curve seen in Figure 10 we have that $\xi_1 = 0$ and that $\xi_\mu = 0$, thus making these solutions valid within filled spheres rather than within spherically symmetric shells. On the other hand, for sufficiently small values of ξ_2 , below that same transition point, these solutions change, since they now have an inner vacuum region, and thus become shell solutions. The part of the limiting curve above the transition point is determined by the existence of a hard singularity of the matter energy density at the origin, while the part of the curve below the transition point is determined by the violation of the DEC.

A word is needed here about the question of the detection of singularities during the runs, and therefore of the detection of the absence of a solution to the problem. When integrating backward from some given values of $\bar{\rho}_0$, ξ_2 and $\xi_M < \xi_2$, the first significant test is whether or not we get a positive value ξ_z of the radial coordinate ξ where $\gamma(\xi)$ becomes zero, and therefore changes sign when we go below that value of ξ . If this does not happen then there is no solution of the problem for that set of initial parameters. Beyond that point, if ξ_z does exist, we still need to find another positive value ξ_1 of the radial coordinate ξ where $\bar{P}(\xi)$ becomes zero. If this does not happen then once again there is no solution of the problem for that set of initial parameters. Finally, during the whole run we must keep checking that $\gamma(\xi) < \xi$, because otherwise we would have a singularity in the differential

The Functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$

Figure 1: The graphs of the three functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$ generated by the numerical development of the solution, for the case $\bar{\rho}_0 = 0.5$, $\xi_2 = 2.0$ and $\xi_M = 1.0$, using backward integration. The resulting values of the two other parameters are $\xi_1 \simeq 0.566$ and $\xi_\mu \simeq 0.412$.

equations and once more there would be no solution.

The numerical test for the presence of a singularity in this backward integration case is to monitor the values of $\gamma(\xi)$ and $\gamma'(\xi)$, to see whether the function $\gamma(\xi)$ fails to cross the zero axis, and therefore whether the function $\gamma'(\xi)$ flips sign during the integration process. If it does, then the solution will develop towards a hard singularity of the energy density $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ at the spatial origin, and hence the numerical integration process can be aborted. In addition to this, we also monitor the DEC, aborting the numerical integration process as soon as it is violated.

When integrating forward from some given values of $\bar{\rho}_0$, ξ_1 and of ξ_μ , again the first significant test is whether or not we get a finite value ξ_z of the radial coordinate ξ where $\gamma(\xi)$ becomes zero, and therefore changes sign when we go above that value of ξ . If this does not happen then there is no solution of the problem for that set of initial parameters. Beyond that point, if ξ_z does exist, we still need to find another finite value ξ_2 of the radial coordinate ξ where $\bar{P}(\xi)$ becomes zero. If this does not happen then once again there is no solution of the problem for that set of initial parameters. In addition to this, during the whole forward integration process we need to monitor the values of ξ and of $\gamma(\xi)$, to ensure that $\gamma(\xi) < \xi$ during the whole process. If this does not hold, then we have failed to arrive at an external vacuum region with the exterior Schwarzschild solution in force, there is in fact an event horizon before a radial position ξ_2 can be found, and the solution is singular.

The numerical test for the presence of a singularity in this forward integration case is to monitor the values of ξ and $\gamma(\xi)$, to see whether the function $\gamma(\xi)$ remains strictly smaller than ξ during the whole forward integration process. If this condition fails at some

The Functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\nu(\xi)$ and $\lambda(\xi)$

Figure 2: The graphs of the three functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\nu(\xi)$ and $\lambda(\xi)$ that characterize the geometry of the solution, for the case $\bar{\rho}_0 = 0.5$, $\xi_2 = 2.0$ and $\xi_M = 1.0$, using backward integration. The resulting values of the two other parameters are $\xi_1 \simeq 0.566$ and $\xi_\mu \simeq 0.412$.

point, then we have just hit a singularity, there is the impossible formation of an event horizon at that point, and again the numerical process can be aborted. In this case the integration process leads to asymptotic divergences of both $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ and $\bar{P}(\xi)$, so that there is no flat spacetime at radial infinity, and thus the asymptotic boundary conditions are violated. Once again, in addition to this we also monitor the DEC, aborting the numerical integration process the moment it is violated.

As was shown in [4], in general the DEC can be written for a fluid as the condition that

$$P(\xi) < \rho(\xi), \quad (48)$$

for all $\xi \in [\xi_1, \xi_2]$, or equivalently that

$$\bar{P}(\xi) < \bar{\rho}(\xi), \quad (49)$$

within that same interval. Using Equation (6) in the matter region we have

$$\bar{P}(\xi) < \bar{\rho}_0 e^{\lambda(\xi)}, \quad (50)$$

and using Equation (19) we get

$$\bar{P}(\xi) < \bar{\rho}_0 \sqrt{\frac{\xi}{\xi - \gamma(\xi)}}. \quad (51)$$

The Functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\bar{P}(\xi)$, $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ and $e^{\lambda(\xi)}$

Figure 3: The graphs of the four functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\bar{P}(\xi)$, $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ and $\exp[\lambda(\xi)]$ that characterize the physics of the solution, for the case $\bar{\rho}_0 = 0.5$, $\xi_2 = 2.0$ and $\xi_M = 1.0$, using backward integration. The resulting values of the two other parameters are $\xi_1 \simeq 0.566$ and $\xi_\mu \simeq 0.412$.

If this condition is violated at any point during the run, then we are outside the allowed region of the parameter space of the model, and once again the run can be aborted.

4 Numerical Results

One can see three examples of solutions generated by the numerical integration program in Figures 1 through 9. The program used here is freely available online [7]. It implements the Runge-Kutta fourth-order algorithm to solve the three differential equations shown in Equations (26) through (28). It runs in quadruple (128-bit) precision mode, and the runs were done with an integration step of $\delta\xi = 10^{-5}$. The results show in Figures 1 through 3 correspond to the initial parameters $\bar{\rho}_0 = 0.5$, $\xi_2 = 2.0$ and $\xi_M = 1.0$, and represent a middle-range value of the energy density. This example is used here to showcase the general properties of the solutions. The arbitrary choice of $\xi_M = 1.0$ can be made without any loss of generality, since this means only that $r_M = r_0$, and therefore represents no more than a choice of value for the arbitrary parameter r_0 , without really determining the values of either r_M or of M .

In Figure 1 we see the three basic mathematical functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$ generated by the mathematics, that is, by the numerical development of the solution of the three corresponding partially coupled differential equations. The three vertical light dotted lines represent respectively, from left to right, the position of the inner interface at $\xi_1 \simeq 0.566$, the position of the extremum point of $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$ at $\xi_e \simeq 1.31$, and the position of the

The Functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$

Figure 4: The graphs of the three functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$ generated by the numerical development of the solution, for the case $\bar{\rho}_0 = 0.314$, $\xi_2 = 2.0$ and $\xi_M = 1.0$, using backward integration. The values of the other two parameters are $\xi_1 \simeq 0.0011$ and $\xi_\mu \simeq 0.0008$.

outer interface at $\xi_2 = 2.0$. The value $\xi_1 \simeq 0.566$ at the inner interface is one that we can check visually in the graph. The same can be done with the value $\xi_e \simeq 1.31$ at the extremum point.

We see that not only $\gamma(\xi)$ is a monotonically increasing function, as expected, but also that it has a monotonically increasing derivative. Therefore, there are no inflection points of $\gamma(\xi)$ within the matter region, in stark contrast with what happens for polytropes. It is visually clear that both $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$ have extremum points within that region, as marked in the graph. We also have the value of the parameter $\xi_\mu \simeq 0.412$, another value that we can check visually in the graph.

In Figure 2 we see the three functions that characterize the spacetime geometry of the solution, namely the basic function $\gamma(\xi)$ and the two metric coefficient functions $\nu(\xi)$ and $\lambda(\xi)$. In all the graphs displayed in this paper, for all the three cases ran, what we see to the right of ξ_2 is the exterior Schwarzschild solution shown in Equation (30), and what we see to the left of ξ_1 is the solution within the inner vacuum region, as shown in Equation (29). The continuity of all functions across the interfaces is in clear display. Note that unlike what we had in the solutions presented in [4], in this case the values $\nu(\xi_1)$ and $\nu(\xi_2)$ at the two interfaces are not the same.

In Figure 3 we see the three functions that characterize the physics of the solution, namely the basic function $\gamma(\xi)$ and the two functions that define the state of the matter, the energy density $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ and the pressure $\bar{P}(\xi)$. Note that $\bar{P}(\xi)$ is continuous, since it is zero outside the matter region, but that $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$, which is also zero outside the matter region, has jump discontinuities at either interface. The graph also shows the radial metric coefficient

The Functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\nu(\xi)$ and $\lambda(\xi)$

Figure 5: The graphs of the three functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\nu(\xi)$ and $\lambda(\xi)$ that characterize the geometry of the solution, for the case $\bar{\rho}_0 = 0.314$, $\xi_2 = 2.0$ and $\xi_M = 1.0$, using backward integration. The values of the other two parameters are $\xi_1 \simeq 0.0011$ and $\xi_\mu \simeq 0.0008$.

function $\exp[\lambda(\xi)]$, illustrating the fact that $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ is simply proportional to it, as expected.

The results shown in Figures 4 through 6 correspond to the initial parameters $\bar{\rho}_0 = 0.314$, $\xi_2 = 2.0$ and $\xi_M = 1.0$, and represents a low-range value of the energy density, in fact almost the lowest possible value of $\bar{\rho}_0$ for the given values of $\xi_2 = 2.0$ and $\xi_M = 1.0$. More than a bit below this value of $\bar{\rho}_0$ there are no solutions to the problem, the other initial parameters being kept the same. The functions shown in each graph are the same as in the corresponding three previous graphs. The major difference is that the inner vacuum region has been contracted almost to zero, so as not to be visible in the graphs. Therefore, in this case we have an almost filled sphere, rather than a shell. The two relevant parameters for the inner vacuum region are both quite small, $\xi_1 \simeq 0.0011$ and $\xi_\mu \simeq 0.0008$. The position of the extrema of $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$ is $\xi_e \simeq 0.162$ in this case.

As one can see in Figure 4, the function $\gamma(\xi)$ hits the point $\xi = 0$ with zero derivative. It does so while having there a very small strictly negative value, not visible in the graph. The position of the point of the extrema of $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$ has migrated close to the spatial origin. It would seem that in a $\xi_1 \rightarrow 0$ limiting situation we would have the maximum of $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and the minimum of $\nu(\xi)$ exactly at $\xi = 0$. As one can see in Figure 5, the very small values of $\gamma(\xi)$ and $\lambda(\xi)$ near $\xi = 0$ mean that the spatial part of the geometry in that region has almost the same spatial metric as the flat space at radial infinity. On the other hand, the negative value of $\nu(\xi)$ indicates a significant amount of blue shift for light arriving there from flat spacetime at radial infinity. As one can see in Figure 6, the energy density is nearly constant in a region around the origin, with its value there given essentially by $\bar{\rho}_0$, and the pressure is also nearly constant in that region, with a value that is just a bit less

The Functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\bar{P}(\xi)$, $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ and $e^{\lambda(\xi)}$

Figure 6: The graphs of the four functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\bar{P}(\xi)$, $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ and $\exp[\lambda(\xi)]$ that characterize the physics of the solution, for the case $\bar{\rho}_0 = 0.314$, $\xi_2 = 2.0$ and $\xi_M = 1.0$, using backward integration. The values of the other two parameters are $\xi_1 \simeq 0.0011$ and $\xi_\mu \simeq 0.0008$.

than one third of $\bar{\rho}_0$.

The results shown in Figures 7 through 9 correspond to the initial parameters $\bar{\rho}_0 = 1.8$, $\xi_2 = 1.2$ and $\xi_M = 1.0$, and represents a higher-range value of the energy density, at a smaller value of ξ_2 . Once again the functions shown in each graph are the same as in the two previous sets of three graphs each. The major difference is that, compared to the previous runs, this value of ξ_2 is on the other side of the transition point at approximately $\xi_2 \simeq 1.33$ that separates two distinct regions involving the limiting curve in the parameter plane, as shown in Figure 10. The two other relevant parameters in this case, those associated to the inner vacuum region, are $\xi_1 \simeq 0.0275$ and $\xi_\mu \simeq 0.278$, so we see that ξ_1 may be small, but is not zero, and that ξ_μ is definitely not zero.

As one can see in Figure 7, the function $\gamma(\xi)$ hits the point $\xi = \xi_1$ with zero derivative, but having there a small but clearly visible strictly negative value. In this case the position of the point of the extrema of $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$ is located close to the middle of the shell. As one can see in Figure 8, the geometry is significantly curved everywhere and there is a small but definite inner vacuum region containing the repulsive singularity at the spatial origin. As one can see in Figure 9, the pressure $\bar{P}(\xi)$ tends to be much larger than in the other cases, and its graph comes close to touching the graph of the energy density $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$. If we decrease $\bar{\rho}_0$ a bit, then these two graphs will touch and then cross, thus triggering a violation of the DEC.

Increasing the value of $\bar{\rho}_0$ beyond the values 0.5 and 1.2 of the solutions shown in Figures 1 through 3 and 7 through 9, with ξ_2 and ξ_M kept at the same values, will not fundamentally change the character of the solutions. It just results in thinner shells, with

The Functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$

Figure 7: The graphs of the three functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\bar{P}(\xi)$ and $\nu(\xi)$ generated by the numerical development of the solution, for the case $\bar{\rho}_0 = 1.8$, $\xi_2 = 1.2$ and $\xi_M = 1.0$, using backward integration. The values of the other two parameters are $\xi_1 \simeq 0.0275$ and $\xi_\mu \simeq 0.278$.

larger values of ξ_1 , still below ξ_2 . The format and characteristics of the graphs of the functions do not change qualitatively. However, making $\bar{\rho}_0$ infinitely large will change the nature of the solutions somewhat, since this $\bar{\rho}_0 \rightarrow \infty$ limit taken at constant ξ_2 will take us towards configurations with infinitely thin and extremely dense shells. These are *not*, however, black hole configurations, since the criterion for the formation of an event horizon is that ξ_2 approach ξ_M from above, which does not happen here since ξ_2 and ξ_M are both being kept constant. Therefore, in this type of limit we get extremely thin and dense shells, but not with enough total mass within a small enough radius to lead to the formation of an event horizon.

In Figure 10 we can see the $(\xi_2, \bar{\rho}_0)$ parameter plane of this family of solutions, for the case with the constant value $\xi_M = 1.0$. That graph shows the limiting curve that determines the allowed region in the parameter plane, shown as a heavy solid curve. In order to have solutions, we must stay above this curve, as indicated in the graph. The graph was obtained by scanning the parameter plane with the numerical program. The variable ξ_2 was scanned with a fixed step of $\delta\xi_2 = 0.01$. The limiting curve was approached from above, with an initial downward step for the variable $\bar{\rho}_0$ given by $\delta\bar{\rho}_0 = 0.1$, which was then decreased exponentially fast, as the limiting curve was approached, until the position of the limiting curve was determined to double-precision (64-bit) level.

As one can see in the graphs, there are two regions of the ξ_2 axis with respect of the existence of the solutions. To the left there is a region where the existence of the solution is determined by the DEC. To the right there is a region where the existence of the solutions is determined by a singularity criterion. The transition point at the position $\xi_2 \simeq 1.33$,

The Functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\nu(\xi)$ and $\lambda(\xi)$

Figure 8: The graphs of the three functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\nu(\xi)$ and $\lambda(\xi)$ that characterize the geometry of the solution, for the case $\bar{\rho}_0 = 1.8$, $\xi_2 = 1.2$ and $\xi_M = 1.0$, using backward integration. The values of the other two parameters are $\xi_1 \simeq 0.0275$ and $\xi_\mu \simeq 0.278$.

that separates the DEC region to the left from the Tooper region to the right, is indicated in the graph using dash-dotted lines. In the DEC region the limiting curve is defined by a violation of the DEC when we go below it. In the Tooper region the limiting curve is defined by the existence of a hard singularity of the matter energy density at the origin when we go below it. The limiting curve behaves as two different powers for $\xi_2 \rightarrow 1$ and for $\xi_2 \rightarrow \infty$, namely approximately as $1/(\xi_2 - 1)^{1.5}$ when $(\xi_2 - 1) \rightarrow 0$ and approximately as $1/(\xi_2 - 1)^2$ when $\xi_2 \rightarrow \infty$.

The condition for the formation of an event horizon is that ξ_2 approach the value of ξ_M from above, which in this case means that ξ_2 has to approach the value 1 in that graph. Such a limit will result in the formation of an event horizon at the radial position $\xi_2 = 1$. Due to the need to stay above the limiting curve, this will also force us to make $\bar{\rho}_0$ progressively larger, so that we end up with a limit in which we have that both $(\xi_2 - 1) \rightarrow 0$ and $\bar{\rho}_0 \rightarrow \infty$. This is the only type of limit that can take us to black-hole configurations. One such possible limit is shown in the graph, as a heavy dotted curve.

Note that one could consider taking a black-hole limit along the limiting curve itself. Since over this curve we have very small but non-zero values for ξ_1 , this will lead to a black-hole configuration for an almost filled sphere, with only a very small inner vacuum region. This is quite unlike the black holes obtained by similar limits in the case of polytropes, which tend to produce very thin and dense shells, located immediately inside the event horizon at the radial position ξ_2 . However, as we have just discussed, in our case here, although there are limits tending to infinitely thin and dense shells, they do *not* produce black holes, which is a bit of an unexpected outcome.

The Functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\bar{P}(\xi)$, $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ and $e^{\lambda(\xi)}$

Figure 9: The graphs of the four functions $\gamma(\xi)$, $\bar{P}(\xi)$, $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ and $\exp[\lambda(\xi)]$ that characterize the physics of the solution, for the case $\bar{\rho}_0 = 1.8$, $\xi_2 = 1.2$ and $\xi_M = 1.0$, using backward integration. The values of the other two parameters are $\xi_1 \simeq 0.0275$ and $\xi_\mu \simeq 0.278$.

It is interesting to contrast this situation with the corresponding one in the case of the interior Schwarzschild solution [3], which is valid only for filled spheres. In that case the intrinsic limitations of that family of solutions make it impossible to take black-hole limits. This is due to the fact that we cannot make $\xi_2 \rightarrow \xi_M$ in that case, since that solution ceases to be valid at all below the value $\xi_2 = 9\xi_M/8$. In contrast to that, if we consider a truly incompressible fluid as we are doing here, then it becomes possible to make $\xi_2 \rightarrow \xi_M$ while keeping ξ_1 constant and quite small, which opens up the possibility of black-hole limits with almost completely matter-filled spheres. However, there are no black-hole limits that tend to *completely* filled spheres of matter, because this would violate the DEC. It therefore seems that all black-hole limits of shell solutions have inner vacuum regions containing repulsive singularities.

It is quite simple to understand intuitively why there is a minimum possible value for $\bar{\rho}_0$ when we keep ξ_M and ξ_2 fixed. Since we are keeping ξ_M fixed, given a fixed value of the reference radial position r_0 we are effectively fixing the value of the total mass M . Since ξ_2 is also being kept fixed, given a certain value of the proper energy density $\bar{\rho}_0$, we must have sufficient proper volume within the spherical surface at the radial position ξ_2 in order to fit the energy Mc^2 within it, at the constant density $\bar{\rho}_0$. If we decrease the proper energy density $\bar{\rho}_0$, then we will need a larger proper volume in order to accommodate the fixed amount of energy Mc^2 within it. The maximum available proper volume at constant ξ_2 is obtained for $\xi_1 = 0$, and therefore for energy densities below a certain minimum value the problem of fitting the energy Mc^2 within the proper volume becomes impossible, and hence no solution exists.

The $(\xi_2, \bar{\rho}_0)$ Parameter Plane for the case $\xi_M = 1.0$

Figure 10: The $(\xi_2, \bar{\rho}_0)$ parameter plane for the case $\xi_M = 1.0$. The limiting curve goes to zero for large ξ_2 approximately as the power $1/(\xi_2 - 1)^2$, but diverges to infinity approximately as the power $1/(\xi_2 - 1)^{1.5}$ at the origin $(\xi_2 - 1) = 0$. The transition point between the DEC region and the Tooper region is approximately at $\xi_2 \simeq 1.33$, with coordinates indicated by dash-dotted lines in the graph.

This argument is valid for all values of ξ_2 , but is most relevant in the Tooper region of the limiting curve, and explains completely what happens there. In the other part of the limiting curve the argument still holds, but in that region there is another, larger lower bound for the value of $\bar{\rho}_0$, brought about by the necessity to satisfy the DEC. In this type of limit we have that $\xi_\mu \rightarrow \infty$ when we make $\xi_2 \rightarrow \xi_M$, as can be seen in Figure 11, where we show both $\xi_1(\xi_2)$ and $\xi_\mu(\xi_2)$ plotted for a black-hole limit taken along and slightly above the limiting curve. The data shown in that graph were obtained for values of $\bar{\rho}_0$ that are a fixed distance of 10^{-4} above the limiting curve. This small distance above the limiting curve, at which the differential system is a bit unstable, being acutely dependent on whether one is to one side of the limiting curve or to the other, is necessary to stabilize the program when running so close to a singular location.

In the graph shown in Figure 11 we can see that, while the parameter ξ_1 has consistently very small values, the parameter ξ_μ , while also staying close to zero for the larger values of ξ_2 , seems to diverge to positive infinity, when we make $\xi_2 \rightarrow \xi_M = 1$ from above. We see therefore that in this problem we have that, while ξ_1 stays close to zero, ξ_μ diverges to infinity in the black-hole limits. In fact, this divergence of ξ_μ seems to be a general property of black-hole limits of shell solutions, for all such static and spherically symmetric solutions, independently of the type of matter involved.

Graphs of $\xi_1(\xi_2)$ and $\xi_\mu(\xi_2)$ on the $\xi_M = 1.0$ Limiting Curve

Figure 11: The functions $\xi_1(\xi_2)$ and $\xi_\mu(\xi_2)$ along the limiting curve of the $(\xi_2, \bar{\rho}_0)$ parameter plane for the case $\xi_M = 1.0$. While the parameter ξ_1 remains very small, the parameter ξ_μ seems to diverge to positive infinity when we make $\xi_2 \rightarrow \xi_M = 1$. The transition point between the DEC region and the Tooper region at approximately $\xi_2 \simeq 1.33$ is indicated by a dash-dotted line in the graph.

5 Conclusions

In this paper we presented the complete solution of the Einstein field equations for the case of a truly incompressible fluid, with a constant proper energy density, in the static and spherically symmetric case. The solutions obtained differ significantly in character from the solutions previously obtained for polytropes, as well as from the interior Schwarzschild solution and its generalizations. In comparison with the case of the polytropes, here there is no local maximum of the energy density strictly within the matter region. In fact, both the energy density $\bar{\rho}(\xi)$ and the derivative $\gamma'(\xi)$ are strictly monotonically increasing functions of ξ until we hit the external matter-vacuum interface at ξ_2 , when they both suddenly drop to zero. The function $\gamma(\xi)$ is also a strictly monotonically increasing function of ξ until we hit ξ_2 , having therefore no inflection points.

Comparing with the interior Schwarzschild solutions, the solutions presented here have one property that is absent from that case, namely they present the possibility of the construction of limits of solutions that result in black holes configurations, with an event horizon and with the internal matter distributed over essentially the whole volume of a filled sphere, a possibility that is absent from the interior Schwarzschild solutions. In our case here such limits can be obtained by making $\xi_2 \rightarrow \xi_M$ from above, with ξ_1 kept at very small values.

Just as the interior Schwarzschild solutions can be generalized to shell solutions, the

solutions presented here include both shell and filled-sphere solutions, the latter being the Tooper-like solutions over the limiting curve. We believe that it is an important fact, established in this paper, that one can, in fact, solve the less trivial problem of matter with a constant proper energy density, even if this problem does not lend itself to a purely analytical solution with results in closed form. Some properties of the solutions can be obtained analytically, but in order to get the detailed solution we ultimately have to take recourse to numerical means. During this process the solution of the problem confirms that the use of the function $\gamma(\xi)$ is an universal and very useful way to deal with this type of problem. The process of resolution developed here for this particular problem is bound to have further applications.

One important aspect of the results presented here is that this solution is one more example of a shell solution with an inner vacuum region containing a repulsive singularity, and one that holds for a new type of problem, with a structure which is qualitatively different from the cases that were previously examined, such as the extensions of the interior Schwarzschild solution [4], the solutions for polytropes [8], which can be seen as extensions of the Tooper solutions [6], and the numerical solutions for neutron stars by Ni [9], further discussed and improved by Neslušan [10, 11]. It thus helps to support the idea that some properties of these solutions, and specially the existence of an inner vacuum region with a repulsive singularity at the spatial origin, may be general properties of the Einstein field equations in the static and spherically symmetric case, rather than particular properties of this or that type of matter.

We end with a word about some limitations of the solution. Note that in general $\rho(\xi)$ consists of all the energy in the matter, including not only the rest energy of the particles involved, but also the thermal energy present. On the other hand, there was no discussion at all of the temperature of the matter during the resolution of the problem. Therefore, except in very low-temperature solutions in which the thermal energy can be neglected, a constant proper energy density $\rho(\xi)$ does not really correspond to a constant proper *rest* energy density. The problem of matter with a constant proper density of rest energy, in the presence of significant thermal energies, constitutes a different problem from the one that we have analyzed here.

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Data Availability Statement

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors hereby certify that there are no actual or potential conflicts of interest of any of the authors in relation to this article.

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